

Genetic Algorithm Applications in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN): A Review

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Abstract

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) has been remained most demanding field due to its application-specific characteristics. There are various applications for WSN and among them some well-known application parameters are energy consumption and life-span longevity for the sake of routing. Genetic Algorithm is a robust optimization technique and possesses the large-scale computational applications. This paper is an attempt to survey of all operational phases of a WSN namely, quality of service (QoS) in routing, clustering, network coverage and localization as well multiple sinks. Additionally, the paper also discusses Genetic Algorithm applications.

1. Introduction

The recent development and rapid advancement in micro-electro-mechanical-systems (MEMS) and nano-electro-mechanical-systems (NEMS) have led the development of miniature, constraint in energy and small-sized devices. These devices are called the sensors. The sensors possess the capability of sensing, processing and communication (Akkaya & Younis, 2005). The sensing ability of a sensor is related to its ambient environment suburbs from where it senses the data. The sensor node sends the partially processed data to a command center through a radio transmitter called sink. The sink is sometimes referred as base station (BS). The sensor nodes send data directly to the sink or by using gateways. This gateway is a data concentration center. Usually, the sensors are irreplaceable once deployed and also have application-specific requirements. Sensors are of various types such as optical, multimedia (Magaia *et al.*, 2015; Akyildiz *et al.*, 2007), thermal, underwater (Ghelardoni *et al.*, 2012), acoustic (Zhi-jun *et al.*, 2009), magnetic or electromagnetic (Akyildiz & Jornet 2010), biological, chemical, seismic and mechanical or vehicular movement (Yick *et al.* 2008; Akyildiz & Kasimoglu 2004; Fadel *et al.* 2015).

A number of wirelessly connected sensor nodes (few tens to thousands) construct a wireless sensor network. The sensor nodes operate co-operatively and have the self-organizing capability. The architecture of WSN can be infrastructure-less or deterministic. Specifically, a WSN has an ad hoc architecture (Yick *et al.*, 2008). The WSN applications cover the wide area in the monitoring and tracking. Monitoring application includes the habitat (Shahi *et al.*, 2016; Polastre *et al.*, 2004; Aboelaze & Aloul, 2005), environmental (Dunbabin & Marques, 2012), surveillance (Deif & Gadallah 2014), military, public, industrious, health (Kranz *et al.*, 2016; Ruxuew, 2015; Zhou & Yi, 2013), business and multimedia (Ehsan & Hamdaoui 2012) as well. On the other hand, tracking application of WSN can be

classified into military, habitat (Arampatzis *et al.*, 2005; Lu & Chan, 2012).

In WSN network, the conventional communication process of a sensor with the sink can be multi-hop or single hop. Sensor send gathered data towards sink by hop-to-hop (multi-hop) communication as shown in figure 1(a). Where, a node A senses the data and sends that data to the nearest neighbor node B, and then the received data is passed through the neighbor nodes C,D and node E, respectively, till the data are received by the sink. In multi-hop communication, the distance gets reduced because of nearness of neighbor sensor nodes. Thus, the consumption of energy minimized (Panousopoulou *et al.* 2016). On the other hand, in a single hop communication each node sends data directly to the sink as illustrated in figure 1(b). It is in the favor of the nodes which have the least distance between the sink and them. But, the nodes which are farther from the sink spend maximum amount of energy to send the data to the sink. So, the energy of a sensor node is consumed at the rate of the distance between the sink and sensor node. Another kind of data sending towards the sink is through cluster. Mostly, higher energy node is selected as the cluster head, which has the responsibility to take the data from the sensor nodes and relay it to the sink (Farooq *et al.*, 2010).

Figure: 1 (a). Hop-to-hop (Multi-hop) Communication in WSN.

Figure: 1 (b). Single-op Communication in WSN.

The lifetime of a sensor is totally depends upon its battery. Due to miniature in size, the sensor possesses small-size battery and when working it gets consumed, resulting node dies down. It is pivotal to save the energy of a sensor so it can perform its operation for maximum amount of time. For the saving of energy and maximizing the sensor network life-span, a significant number of researchers proposed the various algorithms to overcome the energy problem. Most of the research scholars have been proposed the nature-inspired algorithms for the sake of wireless sensor network longevity. The methods used in minimizing the waste of energy includes Genetic Algorithm for optimization the energy in sensor network (EkbataniFard et al. 2010; Ferentinos & Tsiligiridis 2010; Ferentinos & Tsiligiridis 2007; Ramana Rao & Adilakshmi 2016).

2. Applications of Genetic Algorithm in WSN

Inspired from human beings and nature various algorithms have been applied for the solving the complex, multimodal problems in wireless sensor networks (WSN). The GA (Norouzi & Zaim, 2014; Roupec, 2010; Alba & Troya, 1999; Weile & Michielssen, 1997; Mehboob et al., 2014) has an exceedingly extensive choice of applications for optimization the energy of WSN and proved a robust and effective optimization technique for minimizing the useless waste of energy. Significantly, the GA is proposed by the researchers for the purpose of maximization lifetime and energy optimization in WSNs such as multi-objective genetic algorithm (Jia et al., 2009; Sengupta et al., 2013), node placement (Bhondekar et al., 2009; Ozkan & Ermis, 2015; Gupta et al., 2016), efficient data routing, dynamic design (Ferentinos & Tsiligiridis, 2010), QoS (Luo, 2010; Rachedi & Benslimane, 2016), virtualization for in-network data among sensor networks (Khan et al., 2016; Khalid et al., 2014), multi-hop (Zhang et al., 2014; Chatterjee, 2015; Ayaz et al., 2014; Heinzelman et al., 2000; Yetgin et al., 2012), data aggregation (Zeb et al., 2015; Abirami & Anandamurugan, 2016; Balwinder & Dhir, 2015), coverage in WSN, grid

distribution (Sahin et al., 2014; Eris et al., 2014), clustering and placing the time-sensitively multiple sinks (Poe & Schmitt 2008; Mahajan et al., 2014; Khan et al., 2016; Kaur, 2016; Jin et al., 2003).

i. Quality of Service (QoS)

The quality of service can be termed as data delivery guarantee from end-to-end node, reliability and conserving energy. QoS (Wang et al. 2008) can be termed as measurement of service's quality offered to the user/application and it perceived by the user while in the community of networking. The basic and simple model of QoS is illustrated in Figure: 2 (Chen & Varshney 2004; Wang et al. 2008).

A lot of research has been carried out in resolving the QoS challenge (Li, 2015; Othman & Yahya, 2010; Murugeswari et al., 2016; Sahin et al., 2014; Pinto & Montez, 2010; Nazir & Hasbullah, 2013). Mostly, the scholars have focused upon the applications of QoS in time-driven (Abdelaal et al., 2016), event driven and query driven (Ehsan & Hamdaoui, 2012; Chen & Varshney, 2004), continuous and hybrid models (Younis et al., 2004; Tilak et al., 2002; Tian He et al., 2003). Some of the QoS efforts are considered for worth mentioning.

Figure: 2. A simple model of QoS (Chen & Varshney, 2004).

MOGA: EkbataniFard et al., (2010) presented a system of genetic algorithm with the multi-objective (MOGA) for the increment of network lifetime. MOGA based optimization has been applied for preserving the quality of service (QoS) and reliability of end-to-end service in two-tiered WSN. A two-tiered network is formed by two networks whose clusters having the higher energy sensor nodes. These CHs form a network to send the data to the sink. This method is used for constructing a network with higher energy of cluster heads which relay and route the data towards the sink. They used non-dominated sorting in genetic algorithm NSGA-II (Deb et al., 2002; Srinivas & Deb, 1995) for simulation.

CCWM: Mahajan et al., (2014) proposed the QoS based energy conserving and load balancing approach. The cluster head selection is adopted using cluster chain weight metrics. Where, a set of cluster head (CH) is selected with constraint of node degree and regarding the position of the nodes through

CCWM. It uses the local clustering, criterion of selecting the cluster head by feasibility approach and impact of change of base station location on energy.

Li, (2015) suggested an adaptive routing scheme in QoS through GA. This method has been applied for the multicast optimization problem in QoS routing. For the multicast routing an adaptive quantum genetic algorithm (QGA) has been utilized. They reported promising results comparing with (QGACM) (Saitoh *et al.*, 2014) and (QGAFFRA)(Li & Wang, 2007).

The coverage of network is optimized with assuring QoS by sensor deployment in WSN network with the help of GA in (Khan *et al.*, 2012). The authors used this technique for optimal position of mobile sensor nodes for the sake improvement in field coverage and signal transmission. The care has been taken regarding the quality of service (QoS) and coverage uniformity. Thus, the QoS is given as by Khan *et al.*, (2012):

$$QoS = \frac{A_{cov}}{A_T} \quad \dots (1)$$

The QoS is defined as a ratio between covered area by sensors and total field area. The area is supposed to be A_{cov} depending upon the node placement of N nodes with respect to x and y coordinates in the coverage field. The QoS is observed through energy consumption by the low-powered sensor nodes. Further, they designed the network based on the parameters such as QoS, energy dissipation, coverage uniformity fitness, and coverage of sensor deployed field. The promising results have been claimed using these parameters.

Rachedi & Benslimane, (2016) suggested a mechanism of optimization by multi-objective using GA in order to achieve the QoS and security in WSN. The optimization has been carried out using NSGA-II, so that the energy could be utilized efficiently. They reported a scheme applying heterogeneous sensor, which has the capability of sensing audio, video and scalar data. The promising results have been claimed in security scenario and QoS. QoS has been measured in terms of throughput, packet delivery ratio (PDR), delay and reliability of data transmission.

ii. Cluster

A significant number of research scholars have been engaged research using clustering technique in WSNs. The cluster is a group of two or more than two networks where each network group possesses a cluster head (CH). The selection process of a cluster head highly depends upon the energy level of a sensor node, which has the responsibility to take the data from the sensor nodes and relay it to the sink. Usually; the CH is randomly selected from the population (possible solutions) (Farooq *et al.*, 2010).

The CH gather data from the non-CH sensor nodes aggregate the received data and transmit the data to the sink. The working architecture of clustering in WSN is illustrated in the Figure 3. Where the CH is responsible for receiving data from

the sensor nodes and send that data to the sink (Elhoseny *et al.*, 2016; Elhoseny *et al.*, 2015). In cluster 1, the CH is positioned near to the sink. The data is sent to the sink by multi-hop, each node sends the data to the next hop (sensor node) till the receiving at the sink. In cluster 2, the CH is located at the farther point from the sink but the communication of sending and receiving of data is same as cluster 1. The single hop communication and sink is positioned in the middle of cluster as in cluster 3, where the CH has the responsibility of sending the receiving data to sink (Norouzi & Zaim 2014).

Figure: 3.

Sherly & Prabhu, (2016) suggested a scheme of hierarchical routing protocol using genetic algorithm for reducing the energy waste with K-means. The K-means based algorithm is used to balance energy distribution and cluster the network dynamically. A non-static centralized genetic algorithm based clustering approach for limiting the node energy consumption is proposed in Amine *et al.*, (2015). The authors suggested genetic centralized dynamic clustering (GCDC) algorithm for optimizing the locations and number of the cluster heads. Once a CH is selected and found less in energy after completion of a round, the node with higher energy is selected as a CH. The selected CH will be the member of previous CH and perform the work same as the preceding CH.

Baranidharan & Santhi, (2015) suggested a model of clustering hierarchy utilizing GA to achieve energy efficient results. Genetic Algorithm based energy efficient clustering hierarchy (GAECH) for the aim of using the energy efficiently without any useless waste in wireless sensor networks (WSNs). It is used for the purpose of life-span longevity of WSN with the focus on load balancing. This load balancing is obtained to form the clusters through the fitness function which increased both the lifetime and stability period of the WSN. In the observation of life of the nodes in the sensor field different metrics are applied. These metrics assumed as the key parameters for the network longevity, where lifetime of network depends on the First Node Die (FND), Half Node Die (HND), and then Last Node Die (LND).

GAEEP: zahhad *et al.*, (2014) suggested an adaptive clustering protocol using GA with the aim of life-span maximization and stability of wireless sensor network. The system is used to select the most optimum CHs with respect to the location, from where the data is sent with less energy expenditure. Keeping in consideration this scenario, GAEEP has been used in two phases. Where, first round is the set-up phase followed by the steady-state phase. In set-up phase, the optimal cluster heads are selected and sensor nodes allocated with CHs as members. Secondly, the data is collected by the CHs, in the form of frames, is sent to the sink in the steady-state phase.

Hussain *et al.*, (2007) suggested a hierarchical scheme utilizing GA for WSN in for the aim of dissemination of data and increasing the network life time. This aim of maximizing life-span of WSN is supposed for deployment of the scheme for different environments. The cluster formation and management is done with a grave care and consideration of minimum use of energy in routing.

A novel optimization technique using a cluster head agent and GA is proposed in Aziz *et al.*, (2016). The method is defined to find the optimum number of CHs and the positions of CHs and an agent CH is used for the management of distance between the CHs and sink. Comparing with LEACH, it is claimed that their system gives the better results compared to LEACH (Liu & Ravishankar, 2011; Mahmood *et al.*, 2013) using GA in terms of average energy.

GA-WCA: Nie *et al.*, (2010) proposed a system of optimization of cluster head deployment with regard of position and load sharing. The deployment of sensor node is done through the weighed cluster algorithm with genetic algorithm (GA-WCA). In this system, the cluster head has been chosen by GA and the nodes in a cluster is selected by the WCA. When the load of packets more in limited conditions of an ideal load; the load is shared between the cluster heads. This load balancing is meant as the energy balancing of CHs, specially, in the long time monitoring environment at a large scale.

DCHGA: Elhoseny *et al.*, (2015) suggested a clustering approach using genetic algorithm with a dynamic decision making process in a heterogeneous WSN network. Thus, the decision is taken by the DCHGA after every round of the message transmission. Using this method, the claimed the performance of the DCHGA as an incremental of lifetime of WSN considering the stability of nodes on First-Node-Die (FND) and Last-Node-Die (LND). Another technique is proposed by Elhoseny, *et al.*, (2015) for the sake of consumption of energy balancing in heterogeneous WSN networks. The node stability is checked by FND and LND. In heterogeneous WSN the parameters like data processing capability. Initial energy was considered for extension in network life-time. The GA is used for optimization of heterogeneous sensor clustering.

Rao & Adilakshmi, (2016) proposed optimization method among clusters with the help of GA in WSN for minimum

expenditure of energy. The hybridized GA is used with Berkeley Mac (B-Mac), Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), and Local Search Binary PSO (LSBPSO). LBPSO is a method utilized to find out the better results than the BMAC in mobile and non-mobile scenarios. Therefore, evaluation is performed through ratios of average packet delivery, average number of hops to sink, average end to end delays, and jitter.

Jin *et al.*, (2003) suggested an optimization method forming the clusters to reduce the communication distance. Fitness function is improved for optimization. The network is stationary and the sensor nodes are deployed remotely having the capability of managing the transmission power which is based upon transmission range. Each sensor node has the privilege to be the cluster head and send the data to the sink. The sensor node's position measured through Global Positioning System (GPS). The communication distance and energy consumption is given as in Jin *et al.*, (2003) as:

$$E(k, d) = E_{elec} * k + E_{amp} * k * d^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

Where, dissipation of radio energy = E_{elec} and transmit amplifier energy dissipation = E_{amp} (Jin et al. 2003).

EHGUC-OAPR: Liu & Wu, (2013) proposed the energy harvesting routing technique based on genetic algorithm and unequal optimum clustering adaptive performance routing algorithm. In this method, the algorithm is divided into two parts such as one part EHGUC for the creation of uneven clusters and their respective CHs but cluster near to the base station possessed the smaller size. Second part OAPR is reserved for the optimum routing by the BS.

Another approach is applying GA for the optimized routing in two-tiered wireless sensor networks is proposed in (Bari *et al.*, 2009). The only aim of energy optimization was to maximize life time of network. The scheduling method has been used for relaying the data to sink. The integer linear programming (ILP) is incorporated for optimum solution to route the data, while the algorithm has the ability of rapid convergence into ILP to attain solutions for both large and smaller networks.

iii. Coverage and localization

Coverage is one of the important application issues in WSN which demands a deep and grave consideration. The coverage (Vijayan & Gopinathan, 2014) is the total area of covered parts of WSN sensors as illustrated in Figure 4. It is the $L \times W$ of the total area (Zhan *et al.*, 2010). Where, the sensor nodes in the sensor field actively work. During the time of working if a sensor node depletes its energy and unable to participate, then, that dead node is said to be no more in the coverage. Many researchers addressed the coverage problem and proposed different solutions. Since the deployment of wireless sensors in an environment (WSN field), the localization and coverage becomes the essential parameter to be dealt with great importance. The coverage in surveillance of an object is more crucial.

Figure: 4. Coverage in WSN.

Enan & Suat, (2015) presented a scheme regarding coverage for reliable lifetime span of disjoint subsets for the purpose of surveillance. The improving coverage reliability in WSN is by disjoint set covers (DSC) with the optimization of additional variance object. Thus, the single objective problem (SOP) is changed into the multi-objective problem (MOP). In this scheme, the alive or working nodes were kept in active mode and the rest nodes were in the sleep mode for saving the energy.

CCN: The node localization in 2D scenario is presented in Parvez & Divya (2015). The technique of cache node is utilized in WSN using GA for longevity of the network. The GA is used through multi-objectivity feature for the sake of efficient optimization. The node with higher transmission range is named as community caching node (CCN). To monitor the field optimally and efficiently the variations of CCN are low than the variations in n_2 , similarly, the variations are minimum in n_2 than n_1 . The process undergoes through some parameters such as the application-specific, connectivity, sensors-out-of-range error and related to the energy.

An scheme of cache node placement is presented by Sudarshan (2014) using GA. The optimization of cache node assignment with respect to field coverage and charge of cache node has been reported using Scaled Power Community Index Cooperative Caching scheme (scaPCICC). They utilized MATLAB and NS2 for simulation and claimed the promising results in minimum network energy consumption, least delay and average latency.

Coverage maximization and localization of sensor nodes in a WSN field in order to obtain audio placement for close optimal solution to the holes of coverage (Mnasri, 2015). The authors used the acoustic information for localization and to determine the delay a time difference of arrival (TDoA) correlation technique. The environment of NP-hard is kept in the focus. The most considered objectives were increment in

coverage area and audio placement at the cost of detected signal.

Wang *et al.*, (2015) proposed localization in a range-free environment working on GPS. They applied the hybrid technique GA plus Simplex with distance vector hop (DV-Hop) algorithm. It is claimed that the suggested algorithm measures the estimated distance applying the information of DV for network connectivity rather than to send data directly.

MILP: The localization of sink in order to gain optimal path for transmission at the cost of minimal energy usage (Hassan *et al.*, 2014). The proposed method has been used for best location of sink for the sake of reliable and optimal route of message to the sink. Mixed integer linear programming (MILP) has been used with the help of GA for resolution of problem for small-scale wireless sensor networks (WSNs). For reliable routing path, the fitness function of GA calculates the fitness value of reliability of a path. The fitness value of path is kept negative for finding the sink position for the aim of reliable routing path to the sink.

The frame of the solution to problem regarding the sink position using MILP is represented using two binary variables as given in (Hassan *et al.*, 2014):

$$\min \sum_{i \in S} \sum_{j \in N} C_{ij} X_{ij} \quad \dots (3)$$

X_{ij} as a routing variable and i is the point of sensor when it sends data to the sink. The sink is set at point j , and else it set to 0. While, the Y_j is set as the second binary decision variable regarding the sink position and if the sink is at point j it will be assigned to one, otherwise it is 0. C_{ij} is used as cost of path to resolve the problem of shortest path for each i and j .

Abdala *et al.*, (2016) suggested a coverage scheme deploying the homogeneous sensors where the coverage is achieved by finding the optimal and best localization of homogenous sensor in a wireless sensor network. On the other hand, Deif & Gadallah, (2014) proposed a system using non-homogenous sensor for the purpose of coverage. The system is utilized to resolve the sensor deployment problem (SDP) with the help of variable length genetic algorithm (VLGA) for surveillance. For desired results, scalability and convergence, fixed length genetic algorithm (FLGA) is used to cover the finite set of targeted locations. The VLGA and FLGA have been utilized for deployment of WSNs to counter the SDP problem and to get successful convergence speed.

Ghosh *et al.*, (2016) presented a scheme of GA based optimal placement of sink for the sake of maximum coverage in WSN. The scenario has been applied in an ad hoc deployment of sensor nodes, which has the ability to send the data to the nearest sink. The sink has been assumed as the representative of the region of indifference (ROI). The ROI is the intersecting region between the ranges of transmission represented by sinks.

Ebrahimian *et al.*, (2010) proposed k –coverage method for maximizing the network life-time and coverage. Genetic algorithm used for optimal coverage. The scenario is given for monitoring a fully connected area namely k –coverage, while some sensor nodes made as delegates by assigning them off-duty operation. Another technique by Gupta *et al.*, (2016) proposed for the coverage of area of k -coverage and m -connected node localization for monitoring by defining the potential placement of sensor node. The scheme is formulated the network as all sensor nodes as m -connected and k -connected target point. They claimed the promising output from the comparison with the schemes of Mini *et al.*, (2012) and Rebai *et al.*

Unaldi & Temel, (2014) proposed a system of monitoring a 3 dimensional (3D) environment in WSN to maximizing the quality of coverage (QoC) and quality of network (QoN) connectivity. In this scheme a limited number of sensors are deployed and a 3D environment is monitored using GA with mutation operator of wavelet transform (WT). In addition, the main focus is paid upon the maximum coverage, minimum values of path loss and minimum spanning tree. The mutation operator (WT) determines the coverage hollow spaces.

Vijayan & Kumar, (2016) suggested a collision free neighbor assertion (CNNA) for life-span longevity and coverage in WSN. In the CNNA techniques the duplicate packets cancelled which are generated in the multi-path transmission. The scenario is defined as dynamic sensor node placement with a packet delivery ratio, the collision removal and load balancing in the WSN. They used dynamic source routing (DSR) protocol for routing with GA algorithm and PSO.

OCP: Zhan *et al.*, (2010) suggested an optimal coverage problem (OCP) utilizing GA and binary particle swarm optimization (BPSO) algorithms for coverage, energy saving and coverage. For coverage and surveillance, some sensor nodes are selected to be in active state for monitoring. The OCP is represented in two forms which are programmed as 0s and 1s, where 0 means off or sleep mode and 1 means on or active state. To monitor area the optimal coverage problem is given as ($Length \times Width$) for a rectangle area A with a significant number of sensor nodes deployed. They reported promising results compared with probing environment and adaptive sleeping protocol (PEAS) (Ye *et al.*, 2008) and off-duty rule based on coverage (Tian & Georganas, 2003).

iv. Multiple Sinks

Many authors have made research for maximization of WSN life-time using multiple sinks (Jain *et al.*, 2014; C.H *et al.*, 2011). The main aims of using multiple sinks (Vincze *et al.*, 2007) is to get data easily and to reduce the distance of/from nodes to nearest sink and to reduce energy consumption (Bahşi & Levi, 2009). A significant number of researchers used mobile sinks while keeping the rest of the sinks as stationary (Basagni *et al.*, 2009). Some researchers attempted to route the data to the multiple sinks keeping the nodes stationary and sinks as non-stationary (Egorova & Murphy, 2016). The architecture of multiple sinks is shown in Figure 5.

Figure: 5. The architecture of Multiple Sinks in WSN.

Jain *et al.*, (2015) suggested a model of randomly deployed multiple sinks and densely deployed sensor nodes, and assumed the sensor nodes as stationary. The sensor nodes are connected to the sinks through single hop. The connectivity of nodes with the sink/s is determined by the nodes` energy and transmission ability. The distance from a node to the sink/s is defined by Euclidean formula by Jain *et al.*, (2015):

$$D_{ij} = \sqrt{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2} \quad \dots (4)$$

Where, i =Sink and j = Sensor Node.

Multiple sinks are with the help of GA algorithm for the sake of balancing the energy with respect to the energy expenditure.

MASP: The approach with mobility of sink is proposed by Gao *et al.*, (2011) with the prime aim of throughput of the network maximization. They used optimization with the help of GA regarding the assignment of sensor node so that the energy can be conserved. This method is suggested for the efficient data collection by path-constrained mobile sinks in WSNs by balancing the energy consumption. The results have been achieved using OMNET++. Additionally, they used the MASP technique as the mobile sink obtains the data, collected by sub-sinks, in one round as given by Gao *et al.*, (2011):

$$q_{total} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_s} q_i \quad \dots (5)$$

Where, q_{total} is the total data, n_s is the collected data by sub-sinks and i = per round.

GA-MIP: Cai *et al.*, (2010) proposed a system of pre-planned multiple non-static agents using GA in WSN. The system is for gathering data from the sensor in an application-specific field. The sink is made independent to move anywhere in the WSN field to get optimized position which claimed as reduction of task duration and communication cost. The duty cycle of sensor node kept on at the time of working and a

thoroughly investigation is done when some nodes in the sleep mode. They reported a promising results of comparison of GA-MIP with local closest first (LCF) (Qi & Wang, 2001) and mobile agent based direct diffusion (MADD) (Chen *et al.*, 2007) schemes.

v. GA Applications in other fields

Many scholars suggested the GA technique for optimization in WSN (Gupta 2015). Some of the proposed methods are given:

Elnaggar *et al.*, (2015) suggested a GA and ant colony optimization (ACO) based techniques for monitoring the oil pipelines. The technique is aimed for maximizing the pipe coverage, producing the network and longevity of the network. The most selected number of sensors is deployed; each sensor node is set on initial energy and restriction message buffering.

MEMON *et al.*, (2015) suggested a model of path planning for a non-stationary robot in an environment of obstruction using Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and GA. They used PSO for selecting the optimal path and detection of the obstacles in the path of robot from start point (source) to end point (destination). In case of obstacle detection, if an obstacle is found then the robot is moved around the calculated and pre-defined obstacle's boundary, which is assumed as the safe point for the robot by calculating the nearby pre-defined target. The comparison of PSO and GA is done in terms of number of iteration, execution time and path length. Where, the robot reached at destination in short amount of time, minimum number of iterations and choosing the shortest path. Thus, they claimed that the operation of PSO is better than GA in all three parameters.

Potyrailo *et al.*, (2012) presented a scheme of surveillance for homeland security sensing the chemicals and using radio frequency identification (RFID). The sensing of chemicals in terms of toxic and hazards chemical industrial supplies, autonomous detection of lethal vapors in humidity and chemical-agent stimulants, explosives and harmful oxidizers.

Philipose & Rajesh (2016) presented a method of investigation of sensor node placement for railway systems. The method is

used with the help of GA in for the sake of maximization of network lifetime. They used time adaptive-bit map assisted (TA-BMA) protocol, which is considered as the improved form of medium access control (MAC) protocol. In this method, the train is assumed as running at a constant speed and the sensor nodes are static with respect to the movement of the train. The effect of mobility is determined by GA in MAC protocol. The energy expenditure is determined through receive and transmit modes, end-to-end delay, throughput and percentage of sleep mode time. Four sensor nodes have been kept at active state and four in the sleep mode, where active four nodes are placed at the four corners of the railway wagon and a cluster head, the sink/BS is placed in middle. If the cluster head dies the corner node having maximum residual energy becomes the CH. CH receives the data from the sensor nodes aggregates the data and sends to the BS.

Karunaratne *et al.*, (2014) suggested a nominal coding method for a network utilizing the GA in order to optimize in a multicast scenario. The MOGA and VEGA algorithms are taken to resolve the optimization problem. An approach proposed by Murugeswari *et al.*, (2016) QoS based routing through multi-objective evolutionary algorithm (MOEA) in wireless mesh network (WMN).

Shakshuki *et al.*, (2014) presented a cyber physical system using software agents for management of energy for routing. The approach is performed by agent, which locally takes the decision of data aggregation and data processing to the sink. This is done in two phases; first the connectivity of all WSN nodes is generated by Dijkstra's Algorithm and optimal route for mobile agents to route the data to the sink is done by meta-heuristic GA.

Kundu *et al.*, (2016) suggested a system of monitoring the oil availability in the water utilizing the GA. The system comprises the multi-objective artificial neural networks-genetic algorithm and the response surface methodology for emulsion stability. They have gone through the different stages such as stirring time, stirring speed, oil concentration, surfactant concentration and pH to find the oil level in the water.

Table1

Application of GA in WSN

QoS= Quality of Service, M.S= Multiple Sinks, Clus= Clustering, Cov= Coverage, Loc= Localization, S.H= Single Hop, M.H= Multi-Hop, Plat= Platform, Comp. with= Compared with

Reference

	QoS	M.S	Clus	Cov / Loc	S.H	M.H	Plat.	Com. with	Remarks
EkbataniFard <i>et al.</i> , (2010)	✓		✓		✓		OPNET Modeler 14.0	SPEED and SAR	A cluster based approach in two-tiered network with MOGA technique for QoS.
Li, (2015)	✓						MATLAB 7.0	QGACM and QGAFRA	Adaptive Quantum QoS Genetic Algorithm for QoS in WSN
Murugeswari <i>et al.</i> , (2016)	✓						NS2 version 2.34	R-NSGA-II	QoS based routing in Wireless Mesh Networks using Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithm
Rachedi & Benslimane, (2016)	✓					✓	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	QoS and Security in multi-objective optimization in WSN
Mahajan <i>et al.</i> , (2014)	✓		✓			✓	MATLAB	LEACH, WCA and IWCA	Assuring QoS by Cluster Chain Weight Metric based approach.
Sherly & Prabhu (2016)			✓	✓			NS2	LEACH, GAEEP and GABEEC	Energy saving method with K-coverage and K-means by GA.
Baranidharan & Santhi (2015)			✓		✓		MATLAB	LEACH, GCA, and EAERP	Clustering Hierarchy for efficient energy usage.
Nie <i>et al.</i> , (2010)			✓				Not Mentioned	WCA	A mechanism of cluster head deployment through GA-WCA
zahhad <i>et al.</i> , (2014)			✓				MATLAB	LEACH, SEP and ERP	Clustering method for stability and lifespan improvement in WSN
Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , (2016)		✓		✓			MATLAB	Not Mentioned	GA based placement of Sink for coverage optimization
Elhoseny <i>et al.</i> , (2015)			✓				Not Mentioned	HEER, TSEP, DDEEC, ETLE and ERP	Energy balancing and self-clustering method for network longevity.
Hussain <i>et al.</i> , (2007)			✓				Java	LEACH, HCR-1 and HCR-2	A Hierarchical clustering strategy for network longevity.

Aziz <i>et al.</i> , (2016)			✓		✓		Not Mentioned	LEACH	Energy optimization using Agent cluster head method.
Abdala <i>et al.</i> , (2016)				✓			Not Mentioned	--	Sensor deployment strategy for coverage.
Liu & Wu, (2013)			✓			✓	OMNET++	E-WME and R-MPRT	Inter-clustering routing technique for harvesting the energy.
Jin <i>et al.</i> , (2003)			✓		✓		Not Mentioned	--	Optimization for selecting CH for network longevity
Enan & Suat (2015)				✓			Not Mentioned	MOEA/D, GAMDSC and NSGA-II	To maximize network by multi-objective disjoint set covers in WSN
Gupta <i>et al.</i> , (2016)				✓			MATLAB R2012b and C	Mini <i>et al.</i> , (2012), Rebai <i>et al.</i> and Greedy Approach	Coverage and maximum lifetime of WSN through GA
Mnasri (2015)				✓			OpenWiNo emulator	--	Audio-sensors` localization and coverage with Pareto Front GA.
Bari <i>et al.</i> , (2009)			✓				Not Mentioned	MTEM and MHRM	Genetic Algorithm based strategy for network longevity.
Wang <i>et al.</i> , (2015)				✓			MATLAB	Weighted DV-Hop and GA DV-Hop	Maximum Network coverage and localization by Hybrid GA + Simplex Algorithm
Hassan <i>et al.</i> , (2014)				✓		✓	MATLAB R2009a and Java	GA	Sink Location for reliable Path to route the data
Ebrahimian <i>et al.</i> , (2010)				✓			Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Target Location technique in a k-coverage given area.
Sudarshan, (2014)				✓			MATLAB and NS2	ot Mentioned	Cache node Placement technique for network coverage and longevity of network
Zhan <i>et al.</i> , (2010)				✓			Not Mentioned	PEAS and Tian & Georganas, (2003)	Optimal Coverage problem is addressed for the coverage in WSN
Vijayan & Kumar (2016)				✓		✓	NS2	Not Mentioned	Mobile sensor nodes are used for Coverage and Network Lifetime
Unaldi & Temel (2014)				✓			Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Quality of Coverage and Quality of Network for 3D environment in WSN

Gao <i>et al.</i> , (2011)		✓				OMNET++	SPT and MASP-D	Data Collection efficiently in Path-constrained WSNs
Cai <i>et al.</i> , (2010)		✓				OPNET	LCF and MADD	Mobile agent based technique for route planning in WSN
Jain <i>et al.</i> , (2015)		✓			✓	MATLAB	Not Mentioned	By multiple sinks energy balancing method for optimization and WSNs network Longevity
Khan <i>et al.</i> , (2012)	✓			✓		MATLAB	Not Mentioned	Optimizing the network coverage in WSN
Karunaratne <i>et al.</i> , (2014)		✓			✓	MATLAB R2009a	Not Mentioned	Minimization of Network coding through GA
Parvez & Divya (2015)				✓	✓	MATLAB and NS2	Not Mentioned	Cache node placement and cooperative by GA
Philipose & Rajesh (2016)			✓			QualNet. (ver. 7.1)	EA-TDMA and E-BMA	Investigation upon placement of sensor node in Railway system
Rao & Adilakshmi (2016)			✓			OPNET	BMAC cluster	Cluster optimization in WSN

3. Discussion

In wireless sensor networks (WSNs) energy is one of the constraints. Energy has been an open issue to be dealt with the most of the consideration. A significant number of researches to counter this issue have been applied various techniques. The techniques have been applied using Genetic Algorithm. Among them, the quality of service, Coverage and localization of sensor nodes, clustering and multiple sinks are the suggested methods to minimize the energy consumption and to maximize the network lifetime. Quality of service in the WSNs has been proposed by researchers in WSN. It is pivotal for the delivery of data in real time scenario. A few number of scholars suggested QoS techniques using Genetic algorithm (GA). The QoS has been proposed by EkbataniFard *et al.*, (2010) multi-objective GA but work is wanting in coverage, clustering and multiple sinks. While, Mahajan *et al.*, (2014) addressed the QoS in clustering with single object scheme for energy balancing eschewing the multiple sinks, coverage. Over and above, Khan *et al.*, (2012) has been utilized the QoS in coverage and localization of node but omitting the multiple sinks, clustering. The QoS with security Rachedi & Benslimane, (2016) is work for optimization in multi-objective scenario. But the work loses its charm in the areas such as coverage, multiple sinks and localization of sinks and nodes.

Another parameter which has been, mostly, suggested is cluster or clustering in WSNs. A significant ratio of researchers has been engaged in clustering. The cluster technique by K-coverage and K-Means Sherly & Prabhu, (2016) for coverage and cluster head selection. Dynamic selection of cluster head Amine *et al.*, (2015) and energy efficient clustering hierarchy Baranidharan & Santhi, (2015). But they avoided considering QoS, coverage and multiple sinks. The work is limited upon clustering and coverage, shunning the QoS multiple sinks.

The network lifetime maximization and extending the coverage in WSN work is still demanding the grave and sound research. Different studies shows the different scenarios and application of GA in coverage such as the coverage and localization of sensor nodes Wang *et al.*, (2015), coverage and longevity of network Gupta *et al.*, (2016), locating targets in k –coverage Ebrahimian *et al.*, (2010), coverage and cache node placement in order to maximize life-span on WSN Sudarshan, (2014), optimal coverage Zhan *et al.*, (2010), coverage using dynamic sensor nodes Vijayan & Kumar (2016), Quality of coverage and network quality Unaldi & Temel (2014) and coverage with the QoS Khan *et al.*, (2012).

In area of coverage in WSN, the optimization in coverage and placement of sink according to coverage area scenario Ghosh *et al.*, (2016). while Elhoseny *et al.*, (2015) done the self-clustering and balance of energy usage technique for network

lifespan maximization. The method with 100x100 meters applying 50 sensor nodes. Comparing with HEER, TSEP, DDEEC, ETL and ERP protocols the compromising results were claimed. Similarly, network longevity technique by Hussain *et al.*, (2007) to form a hierarchical clustering network. The study shows that authors compared LEACH with HCR and HCR1 protocols. For the comparison, 200 sensors were deployed in 100x100 m² and then 100 sensors employed in the sensor field. The sensor deployment and energy consumption of the sensor nodes` is on the distance from base station and node. The technique is good for small network but it loses its charm for large network and nodes resulting dying quickly. We think the study of Elhoseny *et al.*, (2015) is a bit good for longevity of WSN than the Hussain *et al.*, (2007). Both works avoided the multiple sinks and QoS requirements.

The coverage on the basis of deployed sensor Abdala *et al.*, (2016). Where, 10 tests were presented comparing PSO on 50 sensors and GA on 100 sensors for the coverage. This work lacks in sink placement and its accurate position, optimization, clustering and QoS as well. We think, according to literature review, very less study have been carried out in audio-sensor placement Mnasri (2015).

4. Conclusion

Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) is consists of a number of miniature and resource constraint wirelessly connected sensor node. The WSN has an extensive range of applications in monitoring, surveillance and tracking such as military, commercial and health fields. Undoubtedly, the advancement in recent technologies, the use of WSN is growing in day in day out life. In WSN, the energy consumption is one of resource-limitations. The lesser the energy consumed the greater the longevity of WSN is achieved. Thus, the life-time of WSN depends upon the power of sensor node. The energy expenditure and network life-time is common concern for any application of WSN. A brief survey has been done in the operational phases of WSN such as QoS, Clustering, Network coverage and localization and multiple sinks as well. Genetic algorithm has been used by the scholars for the purpose of efficient and effective routing.

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